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Hungarian engineering students' perceptions about their employability shortly before graduation

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ABSTRACT

The aim was to explore the perception of engineering students of BME (Budapest University of Technology and Economics) on the competencies relevant to their employability shortly before graduation. The survey has been conducted in wider context in three European countries with the same limited number of interviews in a pilot project and the tendencies are being compared.

Following a literature review, in frames of a qualitative exploratory study, the engineering students have been asked about their expectations on future employment and perceived ability to meet the employers' requirements. We have analysed the discrepancy between the students' visions and the employers' needs.

Empirical evidence was collected on skills and competencies required by the companies from the point of view of engineering students. The students were interviewed and the talks were tape-recorded for further analysis. Students were chosen randomly, and so far, 14 students have been interviewed. Thematic content analysis was conducted to better understand the students' competencies.

The paper approaches what motivates students when starting a career. It is clear that both employers and employees claim that hard skills are needed, however, soft-business skills, known as interpersonal competencies would be vital too.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, University-Business cooperation, Engineering Skills

Keywords: employability, competencies, engineering graduates, qualitative exploratory study

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1. INTRODUCTION

In more and more countries throughout Europe, increasing attention is paid to the concept of knowledge-based economy, and within it, to the key role of higher education. Following the Bologna Declaration (1999), higher education has been considerably restructured, with its role becoming more appreciated. Research has proven that European universities have lately been forced to produce graduates who are able to adapt to the latest demands. (Molnár, 2016) The quality of graduate workforce is more and more in focus just like whether graduates are capable of meeting labour market demands. *'...In spite of all the efforts made so far, there is a considerable gap between the skills and competencies of new graduates, leaving higher education institutions and employer requirements...'* (J.A. & H.H., 2008)

In 2016, BME got involved in an international comparative study where it was interesting to experience that this issue does not only concern the students of Hungarian universities of technology but also those of leading European ones. The objective of the research project launched in 2008 was to get a comprehensive picture of the competencies acquired by new graduates of technology. The repeated research launched in 2016 was a longitudinal continuation of the one conducted in 2008, completed with a comparative analysis between the participating countries.

The study involves three European countries: Great Britain, France and Hungary. This paper presents representative research data primarily with respect to Hungary. The target group comprises students of engineering shortly before graduation with focus on their employability, employment opportunities and demands. The students selected belonged to two groups: those participating in the traditional engineering programmes and those who aim for a degree in management parallel to their studies.

Graduating engineering students were asked about their visions, their employment opportunities and acquired competencies, and then it is investigated how this complies with the requirements of European employers. In the research, the empirical experiences of engineering students concerning employer requirements were collected. At the same time, it was also investigated what skills and competencies are needed for their successful career building. Finally, current tendencies are noted, and competency areas for development are explored.

Research methodology applied: personal interviews were made with graduating engineering students using a structured questionnaire, which was identical in all the participating countries. After preliminary arrangements were made, interviews were planned to last 30-40 minutes, which turned out to vary greatly depending on personal motivation level and the individual's personality.

In the first 'pilot' phase, interviews were continuously made from September 2016, involving the adapting, editing and fitting the questions to the traditions of the country parallel with the analytic processing of the results gained. Following the recording of responses, results were analysed in view of the hypotheses.

1.1 Research background

Each of the three countries studied has a quite different higher education structure. In France and Great Britain, about the same number of students (2.4 million) take part in higher education programmes while in Hungary, there are approx. 330,000

students in higher education (see Figure 1). If the proportion of students in the entire population is considered, the difference between the countries is no longer big.

(Source of data: <https://goo.gl/8pdVXK>)

There is a slight difference in the data amounting to some tenths of percentages in the proportion of students in the three countries. Parallel with this, it is important to reveal what requirements employers have throughout Europe towards the newly graduated. *'In order to be able to define student employability, both their personal and knowledge-related skills should be explored.'* (Knight & Yorke, 2004)

1.2 Hypothesis

In formulating our present research hypotheses, we relied on 2008 research results, and formulated our assumptions accordingly. Engineering students formulate more clear and concrete ideas so they apply for fewer but better definable jobs.

It was also assumed that engineering students apply for fewer jobs and spend longer time with a single employer than their peers who completed a parallel management programme, and that the amount of salary is an important consideration for them in job-seeking. It was also expected that in the field of skills, time management, communication and teamwork will require the greatest development.

2. RESULTS

2.1 Career intentions

Most of the volunteers are not actively seeking jobs at present as many of them are already working in some form or other. It is common that future graduates choose one of the companies more closely attached to the university for their internship but after earning their degrees, almost each of them would like to find another job.

The overwhelming majority of the interviewees want to go on working in Budapest or near the capital (Pest county) in any case, and none of them would like to spend more than 2 hours/day commuting. Several of them would like to move to a suburban area near the capital. There was only one volunteer who thought that the location is not important for him as long as accommodation costs are covered by the employer.

Almost all of them wish to try working abroad, many only for the experience, for just a few years but there are also students with much more serious plans: they aim to set up a company abroad and move there with their families. Those who considered having an international career had it in common that they would only go to western

countries. Germany, France, Canada, the USA and Finland were mentioned as potential destinations (note that the last one is geographically in the north).

On the basis of the pre-formulated hypotheses, I expected the amount of salary to be an outstandingly important consideration for jobseekers. The first significant difference between technical managers and 'traditional' students of technology was revealed with this question. Technical managers considered the amount of salary much more important. They have not applied for jobs or accepted offers if they feel that their knowledge is 'worth more' than the amount offered. In contrast, this is not yet a key consideration for most of the engineering students at all. They are much more concerned with the 'nature' of their future jobs and the opportunity to gain experience. Some interns said that their salaries were 'ridiculous' despite the fact that they spent a relatively long time at the workplace in addition to studying. As they said, this approach of theirs is likely to change after they earn the degree, and will only seek jobs above a certain minimum amount of salary.

The survey also revealed that many of them also seriously considered accepting jobs far from their original fields. For many, the working schedule and the workplace atmosphere are decisive factors: they prefer part-time jobs, and a good and direct relationship with the superior and the colleagues. As a demand, several respondents mentioned the methods already widespread and proven in Northern Europe, which could have a motivating effect on new employees, e.g. free coffee, kitchen use, ergonomical, modern working environment and free Fridays. *"In the Norwegian culture, it is particularly important to strike a balance between work and life. They rather have the 'We work to live' than the 'We live to work' approach therefore they finish work very early on Fridays."* (New In Norway - <http://www.nyinorve.no>)

2.2 Job seeking

Most of them have started to apply for jobs relatively late, only during this year, mainly in order to complete the obligatorily required professional practice. There are only a few students who have already been working for years: they typically started to submit applications before or simultaneously with starting their university studies.

The Internet is regarded to be the major source of job advertisements. Facebook and www.profession.hu are two of the most preferred websites. Almost everybody was aware of the functions of the LinkedIn page although few had actually used it before. They are considering actively using the page in the near future as they think it is a network with many advantages. They regard it to be the 'Facebook of jobseekers'.

In addition to the webpages, the different job fairs were mentioned by many as an opportunity for orientation. However, opinions were mixed about their usefulness. Many only go there to look around and see the different employers. Many consider it a problem that in job fairs, companies place professionally unprepared people in their stalls, who may not show empathy towards jobseekers as they often have no idea whatsoever about the students' knowledge, skills and professional fields.

When asked about jobseeking strategies, most of the respondents said that they apply the proven tips and tricks, and are afraid to deviate from them, let alone develop a new strategy of their own. Some of them think that they will certainly get a position if they know somebody who already works or has recently worked for the company. Those who have such a connection have so far had 100% success when applying for a job, and they consider it likely that they will make use of their

connections on other occasions, too. To quote one of them: *'You have a straight path if you know somebody... Unfortunately, this is the only safe method nowadays.'*

Before starting the interviews, I thought the majority would want to work for a multinational company but the results showed a completely different picture. Most of the respondents completed their internship in a multinational company. In the future, the vast majority of the interviewees would not like to work for giant companies. Some would like to start their own enterprises. Many regard multinational companies as an opportunity to gain experience but many realized that a smaller company might also be suitable for gaining the same kind of experience.

The second significant difference between engineering students and technical managers was revealed in the number of the applications submitted. So far, respondents have submitted 25 CVs on average but the technical managers have submitted many more applications than engineering students. It was typical for engineers that the number of their applications submitted varied between 1 and 10. They tend to spend a long period with one employer as a frequent change of jobs is not at all typical of them. On the other hand, the same number varied between 70 and 110 for technical managers. They are characterised by frequent job changing as they make use of the best current offer. They regard themselves as experts who the employers need. Consequently, if they are dissatisfied with something, they leave their current jobs without any scruples and start jobseeking again.

It was typical that the students had about 70% as many interviews as the number of their applications submitted. Most frequent types were telephone and personal interviews which meant a positive experience for them. Only one respondent spoke about going through several rounds of interviews, where English language competence was in focus. It is typical that a significant proportion of the interviews were conducted in an informal atmosphere. Those students who also talked to the foreign managers of the company almost had the impression that the atmosphere was friendly so their previous fears generated by gossip and beliefs proved to be totally unfounded. Following the job interviews, only one student asked the employer for feedback. The others considered it enough feedback whether they had been hired or not, and were not interested in any underlying reasons. Some of them received some unsolicited suggestions to help their development. Two volunteers only realized during our interviews that some feedback from the employer would have been useful for the future and expressed their regret about missing out on this opportunity.

2.3 Competencies

Many thought that professional knowledge, adaptability, language proficiency, flexibility, problem solving and good communication skills belong to the competencies/skills which are most required by employers. Irrespective of faculty, volunteers were of the opinion that only their basic disciplinary knowledge must be extremely solid because students have diverse interests and therefore believe that they acquire the necessary skills/competencies by working for various companies.

Despite agreeing on the crucial role of adequate professional knowledge, they differ sharply in their opinion about the rest of the programme depending on which faculty and which field they belong to. Students of technical management and environmental engineering thought that the knowledge they acquire during the training is far from sufficient. They think that discontinuity is one great disadvantage of the programme;

they just touch upon each professional field, which means that they do not obtain a comprehensive picture or deeper knowledge of any field. This they thought may create obstacles after graduation. This problem is further aggravated by the fact that employers have no idea about the enormous differences between two technical managers graduating from the same institution. Furthermore, it poses further problems that a retiring technical manager cannot be replaced by a newly graduated one owing to the differences between the various training programmes and the lack of expertise. This problem could be solved if they chose a specialisation much earlier as most of them know very well by the end of the first year which fields they would like to pursue and which ones fall outside their sphere of interest.

The results of the interviews supported my assumptions about time management. With the exception of a single student, each pointed out time management as the field in need of major development. In their own view, they are likely to procrastinate, especially at home where they are under no direct supervision. There were, however, some who would be scared of flexitime working hours due to procrastination. As they said: *'if I were given freedom, I might delay everything so much that I wouldn't even get to my workplace.'* *'Procrastination is the vice of human life...'* (Dr Ildikó Takács)

As a cause of procrastination, many identified the unpleasant nature of the task or the constant fatigue they suffer from during the semester. They find it difficult to start working on the task. Many also find it hard to maintain continuous focus, and they do not know how to improve in this. They all agree that this ability of theirs has changed considerably during their university studies, but they do not find this sufficient.

The second most frequently mentioned field to be developed was communication skills. The reason for this was seen in the special nature of the programme, which requires in 90% of the cases individual work from students, and they rarely need to give presentations. This problem leads straight to the third most problematic shortcoming, i.e. teamwork. Many thought that at the beginning, they would find it hard to work in a team because communication between team members would be difficult and university studies did not prepare them for this. Among mechanical engineers, preparation for teamwork has become more and more widespread, which means that students must solve problems in small teams. They favour this practice because instructors can devote more attention to each student and these tasks are considered much more 'lifelike'.

The fact that they are struggling with the above shortcomings is of particular interest since the respondents completely agreed on the utmost significance of good communication skills, and that of the ability of presenting and promoting themselves and being convincing. To summarise the opinions, having good professional knowledge was considered most important alongside the ability 'to sell themselves' as well as being proficient in English and presentation skills (even in English) while German language skills were considered an advantage.

Similarly, everyone thought their individual skills had developed greatly in the last year. They especially stress that subject courses were much more professional and field-specific. This was when the components started to fall into place, and the bachelor programme courses, the necessity of which had been questioned before, started to make sense. By the end of the BA programme, most emphasised their development in presentation, communication skills and time management. Generally, they found the last two semesters of the seven-term programme the most useful.

2.4 Employers' views on competencies

The tendency to almost exclusively hire graduates for vacant or newly created posts is becoming increasingly characteristic of European employers. This tendency is discernible in Hungary, too, in the various job advertisements and in the statistics provided by the Central Statistical Office: in 2015 in Hungary, 82.1% of those with a higher educational degree were in employment, while it was 69.9% of those who had secondary level qualifications and merely 47.1% of those with no secondary school leaving certificates (Hungarian Central Statistical Office, 2015).

Employers give the following reason for their preferences: *'Skills and competencies which graduates acquire during their university training are especially important.'* (UK employer) *'We prefer graduates because they are able to understand and analyse complex facts.'* (Slovenian employer) (J.A. & H.H. Graduate Employability...)

Moreover, graduates are considered much more mature who need less supervision and can accommodate and adapt to the work environment. *'Having studied at degree level makes them more mature... and more employable.'* (UK employer) *'Someone who is flexible and who has the ability to prove themselves.'* (Romanian employer)

In recent years, employers have experienced that the knowledge of newly graduated technical professionals has been lacking in the fields of business and social sciences. This is why they give preference to graduates who have also had such training during their university studies. Furthermore, employers require excellent communication skills in addition to professional knowledge, and the ability to work in teams. Often, however, graduates do not meet these requirements. Employers suggest that by requiring students to do more 'compulsory' teamwork during their studies, students could overcome the lack of communication skills and learn how to work in teams.

3. CONCLUSION

Although the research is still ongoing, some results have already become clear:

Students of engineering are much less interested in the amount of salary they can get than the students of technical management. The former consider obtaining experience as well as studying of primary importance but they think that in the future, they will probably attribute more significance to the amount of money they can make.

Both 'traditional' engineering students and technical managers struggle with time management issues. Many make the mistake of underestimating the time required for a certain task. Many have the problem of procrastination, sometimes they suffer from a lack of motivation to carry out a task. Most often they experience the negative consequences of this: they run out of time during the day, which they try and adjust in the evening, which in the end has a harmful effect on the amount and quality of sleep. Another problem is that many do not have the communication skills employers require. Most European companies are looking for innovative graduates with ideas and initiatives, who are proactive and driven by the wish to bring about a change.

Engineering students submit considerably fewer job applications than their fellow students of technical management. Characteristically, they work for longer periods of employment at a workplace and do not want to change jobs if not necessary. In contrast, technical managers like variety and wish to try themselves with different employers of various kinds. They often look for a new job if they are dissatisfied with something. In some cases, they change jobs every few months.

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